

OPPORTUNITIES FOR BIO-BASED COMPOSITES IN ADVANCED INDUSTRIAL SECTORS

Maya Jacob John^{1,2} and Steve Chapple¹

¹ CSIR, Polymers and Composites, Materials Science and Manufacturing, Port Elizabeth, South Africa

Email: mjohncs@csir.co.za, schapple.csir.co.za, web page: www.csir.co.za

²Department of Textile Science, Nelson Mandela
Metropolitan University, Port Elizabeth, South Africa

Keywords: flame retardant, Mechanical testing, Natural fibre composite,
Thermoset/thermoplastic composites

ABSTRACT

This presentation focuses on the recent research activities dealing with natural fibre composites at the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), South Africa. The CSIR is one of the leading scientific and technology research, development and implementation organisations in Africa. The activities at CSIR (Polymers and Composites division) cover a broad range of research and development in the field of nonwoven technology and composites which include design and fabrication, processing technology, structural analysis and characterization of composite materials. Research programs encompass a wide range of activities from environmentally friendly coupling agents for natural fibre composites to bio-based materials for industrial applications. Current presentation will focus on the use of natural fibre based composites for various industrial applications such as in the aerospace sector. Changing environmental regulations and initiatives such as Clean-Sky, has seen a movement towards replacement of the glass fibre with natural fibres from renewable resources. The development of natural fibre based sandwich panels for use as secondary structures in aircrafts will be presented. Studies related to mechanical and flame, smoke and toxicity testing (FST) will be highlighted. The use of a novel flame retardant system that complies with Federal Aviation Airworthiness requirements will be discussed. The presentation will elaborate on the different strategically tested approaches used in the projects and some significant results highlighting the challenges involved.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bio-based composites comprising of natural fibres are find increasing applications in various industrial sectors: namely automotive, construction and aerospace. The main advantages of using natural fibres in composites include low weight, high strength, comparable specific properties and corrosion resistance. The main advantages of using biocomposites in industrial sectors are:

- Energy and environmental concerns
- Lightweight – an overriding consideration in transportation sector
- Escalating cost of petroleum derived materials and depleting resources

The presentation will elaborate on certain projects focusing on the development of natural fibre reinforced polymer composites for industrial applications and highlight some of the important results.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Flax fabrics, Resins, Nomex cores. Composite structures were fabricated by the process of compression molding. Pre-pregs were placed between the platens of the press and compression molded at required temperatures for curing of the resin (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Preparation of panels in compression molding

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mechanical properties

These included flexural testing and peel test. Flexural four-point bending tests and peel tests were carried out using an Instron Universal Testing Machine, model 3369 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Flexural testing of samples

Flammability properties

Flammability behaviour of the composite panels was done using a Fire Testing Technology cone calorimeter (Figure 3,4 and 5). A constant heat flux of 35 kW/m² was used (horizontal position), and an electronic ignition source was used to ignite any volatile gases evolved from the specimens. The ignition source was removed upon sustained ignition of the specimen. The tests were run for 5 minutes.

Figure 3: Cone calorimeter for flammability testing

Figure 4: Sample for testing

Figure 5: Testing of samples

4 CONCLUSIONS

This presentation investigates the use of natural fibre reinforced composites for industrial applications. A case study is presented in which natural fibre based sandwich panels for aerospace applications were developed. Natural fibre based panels were found to be a feasible alternative to currently used glass fibre panels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the following:
Department of Science and Technology (DST) and CSIR for financial support
AIRBUS (Bremen) for testing samples